

Deliverable D1.4

The repurposing of 2 national SARS-CoV-2 data portals towards national pathogen portals

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Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable	SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (SIB, ELIXIR-CH) The Arctic University of Norway (UiT, ELIXIR-NO) EMBL-EBI		
Authors	Aitana Neves (SIB), Erik Hjerde (UiT), Marianna Ventouratou (EMBL-EBI)		
Contributors	Dillenn Terumalai (SIB)		
Acknowledgements (not grant participants)			
Reviewers	Ilaria Colussi (BBMRI-ERIC) Louiza Kalokairinou (ELIXIR) Henning Hermjakob (EMBL) Patricia Palagi (SIB) Johan Rung (SciLifeLab)		
	[name surname (acronyms)]		

Log of changes

Date	Mvm	Who	Description
dd/mm/yyyy		[Name Surname (acronyms)]	
dd/mm/yyyy		[Name Surname (acronyms)]	

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the creation of two new national pathogen data portals for Switzerland and Norway. These portals were inspired by the Swedish Pathogens Portal, launched in September 2023 by SciLifeLab¹, and are part of a growing network of national COVID-19/Pathogen Data Portals.

National pathogen portals are web sites that serve as community hubs for pathogen related information, guidelines, and light-weight data services and resources. Their content is relevant to, and often developed and operated by, users or organisations in the local country, while also providing a bridge to international resources such as the EMBL-EBI Pathogens Portal and other national data portals.

The Swiss Pathogens Portal, launched on 29 August 2024, was developed by SIB, the Swiss ELIXIR node, who already runs and hosts the Swiss Pathogen Surveillance Platform (SPSP.ch) enabling near real-time controlled access of pathogen sequencing data and their associated clinical/epidemiological metadata. SIB created a HUGO² official template theme to assist the development of other local Pathogens Portals; this is publicly available on the GitHub repository³ and includes many advantages outlined in the report below. The Swiss Pathogens Portal includes pathogen and infectious disease dashboards, FAIR data sharing guidelines, Swiss pathogen data catalogues hosted within national data hubs and bioinformatics resources, among others. Its goal is to better support research data management practices in the infectious diseases domain and foster collaborations and synergies. The creation of the Swiss Pathogens portal will enable capturing and highlighting existing efforts, for example, by connecting the SPSP data catalogue to the Pathogens Portal hosted by EMBL-EBI.

The Norwegian Pathogens Portal, launched on 9 September 2024, developed by the Arctic University of Norway (UiT), a partner of ELIXIR Norway, aims to cover the need for an infrastructure that supports systematic and FAIR sharing of pathogen data and contextual metadata in Norway. The portal includes national resources related to pathogen research with a focus on human pathogens, but it also links to food, water and vector borne diseases and non-human related pathogens. The Norwegian Pathogens Portal uses a powerful React framework, NextJS, for frontend development, while Notion is used for content management, providing thus a user-friendly interface. Many of the functionalities of the portal are aligned with those of the Swedish and the Swiss portals.

The different technological frameworks chosen by the two portals showcased in this deliverable underline the importance of flexibility and adaptability in any framework or

¹ SciLifeLab is the Swedish national life science infrastructure, <https://www.scilifelab.se>

² <https://gohugo.io>

³ <https://github.com/sib-swiss/hugo-pathogens-portal>

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template to reflect and meet the needs of each country and community facing unique challenges, be it cultural, technological or related to infrastructure availability.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures practice that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal.	Yes
	2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	No
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform	No
	4. Engagement so that stakeholders (RI, national centres, policy makers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	Yes
Objective 2 Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres	1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.	No
	2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.	Yes
	3. Demonstrated transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve the research needs of epidemiology and public health.	Yes
	4. Demonstrated assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the on-going European VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.	No

<p>Objective 3</p> <p>Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19</p>	<p>1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility, and disease pathways.</p>	No
	<p>2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease resources based on mappings across resources and research domains.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness, including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern</p>	<p>1. Broad uptake of viral <i>Data Hubs</i> across Europe deliver an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.</p>	No
	<p>2. Infrastructure and quality workflows mobilised and shared to produce open, normative variant data that is incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision making.</p>	Yes
<p>Objective 5</p> <p>Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS)</p>	<p>1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on work of other guideline producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).</p>	Yes
	<p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p>	Yes

	3. Alignment (both policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.	Yes/No
	4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps, and to exchange experiences and knowledge.	Yes

3. Methods

Deliverable scope. This is an add-on deliverable to the original project resulting from the realisation that there is a need for supporting the network of national pathogens portals, a natural continuation from the COVID-19 Data Portals and the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. Sweden was the first country to convert its national COVID-19 Data Portal to a Pathogens Portal, setting the precedent (and sharing experience and open source code) with other national portals. While not all national coordinators had the funding or national approval to proceed with the creation of a national portal, Norway and Switzerland benefited from their participation to BY-COVID and utilised some of their funds towards this goal. Deliverable 1.4 was added to WP1 in February 2024 and is also linked to WP3.

Methodology. SciLifeLab has set up the [Swedish Pathogens Portal](#) (PP) based on the HUGO technological framework⁴. HUGO is a popular static site generator that enables rapid builds, editor-friendly markdown-based content generation, and customizable content management within flexible themes. The code from the Swedish PP is publicly available on [github](#).

For this Deliverable:

1. Each beneficiary assessed the functional needs for their local PP.
2. These functional needs were then mapped to IT constraints.
3. Based on the identified IT constraints, various technological frameworks were investigated, including HUGO. At this stage, the beneficiaries had meetings together and with SciLifeLab in order to compare assessments, discuss potential gaps and support each other in selecting the best framework for their own needs.

⁴ <https://gohugo.io>

4. Each beneficiary implemented their planned functional features, started including dedicated content and published a first release of their national PP.

The Swedish, Swiss and Norwegian PP have been listed on the EMBL-EBI PP:

<https://www.pathogensportal.org/national-data-portal>.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Swiss Pathogens Portal

4.1.1 Context

In Switzerland, the Swiss Pathogen Surveillance Platform ([SPSP.ch](https://spsp.ch)) is a secure One-health online platform that enables near real-time sharing under controlled access of pathogen sequencing data and their associated clinical/epidemiological metadata. SPSP is currently mandated by the Federal Office of Public Health to centralise all the SARS-CoV-2, Influenza and RSV surveillance/sentinella genomic data. It also has an agreement with the Federal Office of Public Health and Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office to include human/animal/foodborne bacteria of public health interest and antimicrobial resistance predictions from 2024 onwards.

SPSP is hosted and developed by SIB, the Swiss ELIXIR node, in collaboration with the microbiology and virology laboratories of all Swiss University Hospitals, being closely connected with the Swiss clinical data provider community. Currently, SPSP has a private portal displaying sensitive data to its users (including identifiers), and a public portal (public.spsp.sib.swiss) that enables all of its data catalogue, encompassing also sensitive fields, to be discoverable in line with FAIR principles. The existing SPSP ethical and legal framework regulates data access and reuse of sensitive data, whereas non-sensitive data are published openly on the ENA.

Swiss efforts on One Health pathogens data management however go beyond SPSP and encompass various activities and resources notably led by SIB affiliated groups (e.g. [nextstrain](#), [CoVpectrum](#), [CoVariants](#), [V-pipe](#), [loculus](#)). A Swiss Pathogens Portal would enable capturing and highlighting all these efforts in a centralised fashion and also foster synergies between these resources and scientists. It would eventually also provide a means to connect the SPSP data catalogue to the EMBL-EBI [Pathogens Portal](#).

4.1.2 Work accomplished

As explained above, Switzerland already hosts various dashboards developed within SIB groups. In particular, the public portal of SPSP enables anyone to find data within the SPSP controlled access data hub. After discussing with SciLifeLab and UiT developers, it was

therefore agreed that a static website would be sufficient to enable showcasing dashboards, and to facilitate the finding and accessing of data, projects and training material.

Available Datasets

Swiss Pathogens Portal: supporting researchers for pandemic preparedness and response / Share and Access Data / Available Datasets

Access-controlled datasets

This is a manually curated list of available datasets with controlled-access. New datasets are added on an ongoing basis. If you would like your project to be listed here, please get in touch with us.

10 entries per page Search:

Name	Access data catalog	Data access documentation	Contact
Swiss Pathogen Surveillance Platform	https://public.spsp.sib.swiss/	https://public.spsp.sib.swiss/docs/data-access-and-re-use.html	aitana.neves@sib.swiss ; aegli@imm.uzh.ch

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entry « < 1 > »

Pathogens Portal

Results for Switzerland

Pathogen sequences 60,364 results

[View all 31,467 results in Sequences](#) [View all 1,188 results in Analysis](#) [View all 16,259 results in Raw reads](#) [View all 11,450 results in Assembly](#)

Samples 17,507 results

[View all 17,507 results in Samples](#)

Outbreak 12,246 results

[View all 236 results in Sequences](#) [View all 338 results in Analysis](#) [View all 5,880 results in Raw reads](#) [View all 5,792 results in Samples](#)

Datasets available from research groups in Switzerland

The table below lists the latest publications from research groups in Switzerland that are on [Europe PubMed Central](#) and mention a dataset (cf. data sources on the left panel).

Data sources	Publication
All data (1920) Figshare (65) Zenodo (235) Github (722) Dryad (17) Gene Expression Omnibus (151) Protein Data Bank (296) Proteome Xchange (15) SASBDB (3) Electron Microscopy DB (76) ENA (72) Open Science Framework (265) Experimental Factor Ontology (3)	10 entries per page Search: <input type="text"/> <hr/> "I will take part in the revolution with our people": a qualitative study of healthcare workers' experiences of violence and resistance after the 2021 Myanmar coup d'etat. Haar RJ, Crawford K, Fast L, Win TH, Rubenstein L, Blanchet K, Lillywhite L, Tint-Zaw N, Mon MM. undefined DOI: 10.1186/s13031-024-00611-7 <hr/> "The Tragedy of the Commons": How Individualism and Collectivism Affected the Spread of the COVID-19 Pandemic. Maaravi Y, Levy A, Gur T, Confino D, Segal S. undefined DOI: 10.3389/fpubh.2021.627559 <hr/> "You need to dispose of them somewhere safe": Covid-19, masks, and the pit latrine in Malawi and South Africa.

Figure 1. Screenshot showing Available Datasets on the Swiss Pathogens Portal. <https://pathogensportal.ch/access-data/datasets/>

In order to facilitate future developments and deployments by others, the SIB started by creating a HUGO official template theme for local Pathogens Portals. It is publicly available on the [team's github](#) repository and comes with many advantages:

- Increases reusability, notably thanks to country-specific metadata moved to a configuration file.

- Allows for component generalisation.
- All hard coded parts have been replaced with dynamic code, easily configurable by others.
- Includes native support for multilingual portals.
- Events can easily be added using markdown files.
- All publications from the country specified in the config file are retrieved from Europe Pubmed Central if they mention a dataset, and then classified according to the mentioned repositories (e.g. zenodo, Figshare etc). (cf. Figure 1, “Datasets available from research groups in Switzerland”)
- Includes usage of a cache to avoid very large queries.
- Implementation of native breadcrumbs.
- Implementation of tags.
- Implementation of categories for events.
- Possibility to support external hosting of dashboards with a redirect_url.
- Social media links added in the config file.
- Inclusion of "Last modified" information and "Edit this page" link on each page.
- Added submenu items based on identifier.
- Added link to github repository.
- Added customisation of logo, institution logo and favicon.
- Paginated results for tag or category search results.
- Retrieval of pathogens portal statistics.

The Swiss Pathogens Portal was developed to support infectious-diseases researchers by providing a one-stop portal for:

- Accessing pathogen and infectious diseases data dashboards that are maintained by Swiss research groups and federal authorities.
<https://pathogensportal.ch/dashboards/>
- Guidelines for FAIR data sharing by Swiss data providers.
<https://pathogensportal.ch/access-data/share-data/>
- Listing Swiss pathogen data catalogues hosted within national private data hubs and on the EMBL-EBI Pathogens Portal (cf. Figure 1, “Pathogens Portal: results for Switzerland”).
<https://pathogensportal.ch/access-data/datasets/>
- Bioinformatics resources developed within SIB groups and support services.
<https://pathogensportal.ch/analyse-data/>
- Finding documentation and training material on e.g. FAIR research data management and pathogens bioinformatics; listing upcoming events of relevance
<https://pathogensportal.ch/analyse-data/training-material/>
<https://pathogensportal.ch/events/>
- Listing infectious diseases and antimicrobial research projects, which are funded by major funding agencies in Switzerland.

Altogether, it is envisioned that the Swiss PP will support better research data management practices within the infectious-diseases field, and also foster collaborations, data sharing and synergies by creating a forum for discussion and information exchange.

4.2 Norwegian Pathogens Portal

4.2.1 Context

There is a lack of an infrastructure for systematic and FAIR sharing of pathogen data and the contextual metadata in Norway. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the Arctic University of Norway (UiT) as a partner of ELIXIR Norway was approached by data producers such as the National Institute of Public Health (NIPH) to support deposition of SARS-CoV-2 data to public repositories. This included implementation of decontamination pipelines for removal of human host DNA from the datasets in Trusted research environments, structuring metadata and brokering submission (submitting on behalf of the data owners) of data to the European Nucleotide Archive. After the pandemic, ELIXIR Norway has continued to build up the data submission brokering service towards national data producers and are brokering submissions of pathogen sequence data from multiple pathogens.

Together with NIPH, ELIXIR Norway recently received a 4-year grant from the National Research Council to build a Norwegian Pathogen Platform, which will include an infrastructure for data sharing, analysis, metadata management, and data brokering. This will be connected to the Pathogens Portal Norway which will be the entry point for end users. During the BY-COVID project, UiT received additional funding to build a first version of the national Pathogens Portal.

4.2.2 Work accomplished

On September 9 2024, the Pathogens Portal Norway (PPN) became available online at <https://pathogens.no/>. The portal currently lists national resources related to pathogen research as well as surveillance in a one-health perspective. The focus of national resources on human pathogens is naturally reflected in the content, however the portal also links out to resources related to food, water and vector borne diseases, as well as non-human related pathogens.

A comprehensive assessment of functional requirements specific to the national pathogen portal needs was conducted. These requirements were carefully mapped to IT and resource constraints, considering factors such as scalability, maintainability, future expandability and integration capabilities. The PPN was implemented using a modern, performance-oriented tech stack. NextJS (<https://nextjs.org/docs>), a powerful React framework, was chosen for the frontend development, enabling server-side rendering and Search Engine Optimizations whilst also allowing for fluid client side interactivity for the users. To streamline content management, Notion (<https://www.notion.so/product>) was

integrated as the CMS, providing a user-friendly interface for researchers and administrators to update and maintain the portal's content efficiently. To align with our partner portals from Sweden and Switzerland we have implemented many of the functionalities to the portal as mentioned for the Swiss portal in section 4.1.2. In addition, the PPN pages link directly to relevant information in Prosjektbanken, the national research project database (<https://prosjektbanken.forskingsradet.no/en>) and CRISTIN, the national research information system containing information about Norwegian research (<https://app.cristin.no/>).

As a result from large projects related to Research Data Management (RDM) such as ELIXIR Converge (<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/converge>) and BioMedData (<https://elixir.no/organization/biomeddata>), the portal dedicates a large section to RDM, with sub pages covering topics such as FAIR data sharing and relevant tools, workflows and databases recommended by the national ELIXIR support desk. The PPN has been presented at meetings with national stakeholders including the Pandemic Centre (<https://www.uib.no/en/pandemic>). We envision the portal to be the starting point for finding nation wide information about pathogen research and surveillance, and to offer a portal for sharing research data.

5. Results

The first version of the [Swiss Pathogens Portal](#) was released on 29 August 2024. It was announced at the Steering Board meeting of the SIB Centre for Pathogen Bioinformatics.

The first version of the [Norwegian Pathogens Portal](#) was released on 9 September 2024. The portal has been presented at two meetings with stakeholders representing the National Institute of Public Health and the Pandemic Centre in Norway. It has also been announced through all ELIXIR Norway outreach channels.

6. Discussion

The selection of different technological frameworks by the two beneficiaries, based on their distinct functional specifications and needs, underscores the critical importance of maintaining **flexibility** in any framework or template. Each country and community often faces unique challenges, cultural factors, and local infrastructure that require tailored solutions. Different countries may also choose to include specific data services and -resources that require technologies not necessary by other national portals. What works effectively in one region may not be suitable in another, and rigid frameworks can stifle innovation or fail to meet specific local requirements. By keeping frameworks adaptable, it ensures that countries can modify or extend their implementation strategies to suit their own context, ultimately enhancing the success and sustainability of their initiatives. This

adaptability also promotes **scalability** and **interoperability**, allowing for integration with evolving technologies and localized needs, whether in data collection, user interface, or system architecture.

7. Conclusions

The two beneficiaries have each successfully implemented and released a national pathogens portal. Importantly, these resources will be maintained and further developed. Within the scope of the NIH-funded project “Pathogen Data Network” (grant number U24AI183840), a global distributed network of local pathogens portals will be established. SciLifeLab will be in charge of providing a reference software implementation to facilitate deployment and accelerate resource buy-in. The Swiss and Norwegian nodes will co-lead a Community of Practice of local pathogens portals, providing support and a forum of discussion for novel ideas and exchange of implementation solutions.

8. Next steps

Swiss Pathogens Portal.

It is planned to have content added on a regular basis, notably through the activities of the recently launched SIB [Centre for Pathogen Bioinformatics](#), that will be in charge of its maintenance and content management. Additional features will also be integrated, notably to enable data discoverability from the central PP hosted at EMBL-EBI.

Norwegian Pathogens Portal.

As already mentioned, ELIXIR Norway has received national funding to continue to develop a national pathogen platform. The platform will consist of a Pathogens Data Hub, and the Pathogens Portal. We will add new topics and link to more national resources, and we aim to support national researchers to visualise their research data through the Pathogens Portal dashboards.

Swedish Pathogens Portal.

SciLifeLab will continue to develop the Swedish Pathogens Portal (which is not part of this deliverable, but mentioned here for context), taking long term responsibility for its maintenance and user support. New features will be developed, and underlying compute- and storage infrastructure will be strengthened. The Portal software will be further refined in close collaboration with the Swiss and Norwegian portal teams, and with other new national portals started through the NIH-funded “Pathogen Data Network” mentioned above.

9. Impact

National data portals like **pathogens.se** (Sweden), **pathogens.no** (Norway), and **pathogensportal.ch** (Switzerland) play a crucial role in advancing public health, scientific research, and global pathogen surveillance. These portals serve as centralised, accessible platforms where researchers, healthcare professionals, and policymakers can access dashboards on pathogens, including emerging infectious diseases and antimicrobial resistance in the future. These portals also enhance transparency and accessibility of pathogen-related information to the public, helping increase awareness and improve preparedness for both national and international health challenges. For the data providers and scientific community, national portals allow for better data management practices and pave the way towards collaboration and data sharing between countries.